

Influence of backbone rigidity on the surface rheology of acrylic Langmuir polymer films

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Abstract

We present an experimental study on the surface rheology of ultrathin films of poly(tert-butylacrylate) (PTBA) and poly(tert-butylmethacrylate) (PTBMA) for which steric hindrance imposed by the methyl group leads to a large intrinsic rigidity of the polymer chain. Whilst PTBA films show weak temperature dependence, PTBMA films undergo a solid-liquid transition at a temperature well below T_g , the glass transition temperature of the bulk polymer. The peculiar behaviour observed for the shear moduli beyond the fluid-solid transition is similar to that observed recently with dispersions of soft colloidal spheres [D. A. Sessoms, et al., *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A*, 2009, 367, 5013-5032], where, upon cooling, the system undergoes first a glass transition, followed by a jamming transition. The transition that we observe in PTBMA films could be similar or, alternatively, could be analogous to the glass transition of the bulk polymer.

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Introduction

The molecular conformation of linear polymer chains is determined by the restricted rotation of molecules around single bonds.^{1,2} Steric hindrance imparts conformational persistence to the chain backbone, which subsequently controls the macroscopic elasticity.^{2,3} As concerns chain dynamics, in bulk systems, motion occurs through the available free volume, which is significantly larger in the melt than in the glass, where individual chains become somehow arrested in a solid-like dynamical state.^{4,7} The temperature range for processability and usability in technological applications is mainly determined by this glass transition temperature, which is influenced by the chemical structure of the polymer. Although the determination of the glass transition temperature, T_g , depends on the experimental observable,⁸ its commonly accepted dynamical definition refers to the temperature at which the free energy exceeds the activation energy necessary for segmental motion, allowing chain segments to slide past each other when forces are applied. Obviously, bulky side groups slow-down this flow, hence increasing T_g in bulk. Furthermore, for films thinner than the chain size, the dominant dynamics could be the motion of dangling loops, which would be much faster than constrained motions in bulk.⁹ Consequently, polymers in thin films have a lower glass transition temperature with respect to the bulk value.¹⁰ Since new insights into the nature of the glass transition and its connection with spatial cooperativity could be inferred from the changes in behavior observed at reduced dimensionalities, the fascinating feature of T_g -drop in thin films has been profusely studied in the last few years, both experimentally^{10,11} and theoretically.¹² Langmuir polymer films (LPFs) spread at the air/water interface provide an adequate scenario for testing dynamical polymer behavior in quasi-two dimensional space (see ref. 13 for a recent review). LPF properties can be easily deduced from the surface pressure¹⁴ and from mechanical responses to external stimuli.^{14,15}

Acrylic polymers are a family of thermoplastics distinguished by their transparency, rigidity and resistance to breakage. They have a hydrophobic backbone with lateral side carbonyl groups, which impart partial hydrophilic character. Lateral substituents are also crucial for imposing steric constraints, which define intrinsic rigidity and conformational persistence along the linear sequence. Methacrylates differentiate from acrylates by a secondary methyl-lateral group which leads to a higher hydrophobicity and stronger intrinsic rigidity. Indeed, the glass transition temperature of methacrylates is much higher than that of their homologous acrylates. Here, we present a study of the surface viscoelasticity of LPFs of two acrylic polymers with significantly different intrinsic rigidities. Poly(tert-butylacrylate) (PTBA, $T_g \approx 35^\circ\text{C}$) was chosen to be quite flexible and close to fluid at room temperature, while its methacrylate homologue poly(tert-butylmethacrylate) (PTBMA, $T_g \approx 118^\circ\text{C}$) is a stiff solid. As expected, we observe evidence of mechanical dichotomy, but at lower temperatures than in bulk. These results constitute a first piece of experimental evidence of the control exercised by steric hindrances on the macroscopic mechanics in the case of reduced dimensionality (quasi-two dimension).

Materials and methods

Polymers

We have chosen two different acrylic polymers, i.e. poly(tertbutylacrylate) (PTBA) and poly(tert-butylmethacrylate) (PTBMA), with identical lateral group (tert-butyl) but different hydrophobicities imposed by the methyl group. This additional methyl moiety provides a higher internal density and conformational rigidity. PTBA and PTBMA were purchased from Polymer Source (Canada). Highly monodisperse samples with a similar molecular weight M_w were chosen in order to make reliable comparisons. In the case of PTBA we have studied samples with $M_n = 1.44$ and 287 kDa (polydispersity index $PDI = M_w/M_n = 1.13$ and 1.14 respectively). In the case of PTBMA, two samples with $M_n = 1.45$ and 211.5kDa ($PDI = 1.08$ and 1.30, respectively) have been studied. All the samples were dissolved in chloroform (99% purity, purchased from Sigma-Aldrich) at a concentration close to 0.1mgmL^{-1} for all the experiments.

Langmuir film preparation

Langmuir films were prepared by the dropwise addition. In a typical experiment the polymer solution is spread on the water surface (from a Milli-Q unit; resistivity higher than $18\text{ m}\Omega\text{ cm}^{-1}$, organic matter content lower than 2 ppb, surface tension 72.6 mNm^{-1} at 20°C). Small aliquots are successively added and the solvent left to evaporate, thus ensuring equilibrium aliquots and no multilayer formation. ¹⁶ A $10\mu\text{L}$ Hamilton syringe was used to deposit the polymer onto the water surface.

Surface pressure isotherms

Surface pressure measurements were performed in a Langmuir balance (NIMA 702 BAM, Nima Technology, UK). The Teflon trough has large dimensions (72 cm long \times 10 cm wide \times 5 mm deep) ensuring adequate spreading. A paper Wilhelmy plate ensuring zero contact angle (Whatman CHR1, 21 mm effective perimeter) is attached to a surface tension sensor (PS4, Nima) with a precision $\pm 0.1\text{mNm}^{-1}$. Temperature was controlled in the subphase at an accuracy better than $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ at 25°C . The $\Pi - \Gamma$ isotherms are obtained varying the surface concentration Γ by dropwise addition of successive polymer aliquots from the spreading solution as explained above.

The compression modulus E_0 , associated to the elastic energy stored by the surface layer upon compression, i.e. when more material is added onto the water subphase, is obtained by direct derivation of the equilibrium surface pressure-surface concentration Γ isotherm, as given by eqn (1)

$$E_0 = -\Gamma \left(\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial \Gamma} \right)_T \quad (1)$$

Interfacial shear rheology

The interfacial shear properties of the thin polymer films were studied by using a standard rotational rheometer (Anton Paar Physica MCR 301) with an embedded interfacial rheology system (IRS).¹⁷ The IRS consists of a biconical disk (disk radius $R_2 = 34.14$ mm , cone angle $\alpha = 5^\circ$ and cone penetration depth $h_2 = 2.205$ mm) which is coupled to the top-driven motor and transducer unit of the rheometer. The measuring cell consists of a cup made of glass (cup inner radius $R_1 = 40.00$ mm and cup height $H_1 = 45.00$ mm), covered by an insulation jacket and fixed to the bottom part of the rheometer with a flange. The whole device is mounted on an antivibration table (Technical Manufacturing Corp., MA, USA). Once the water subphase is poured into the cup, the polymer is spread on it and the bicone is positioned at the interface by using the normal force transducer. The position h_1 where the bicone tip contacts the water subphase, i.e. the water level, is measured by the sudden change experienced by the normal force transducer unit. Then, the bicone mid-plane is located at the interface fixing the bicone tip position at $h_0 = h_1 - h_2$. We have performed strain-controlled experiments of the polymer films by using the oscillation mode, in which the bicone oscillates at a controlled angular frequency ω and strain amplitude γ while the cup remains stationary. During the measurements, the temperature is controlled by a Peltier and the cell is covered by a cap in order to prevent evaporation and contamination.

Since interfacial and bulk flows are coupled, the interfacial stresses are dissipated into the bulk water phase. Thus, after data acquisition we have performed the numerical evaluation of the interfacial rheological parameters by using the commercial software developed by Anton Paar¹⁷ on the basis of the interfacial and bulk velocity distributions obtained by Oh and Slattery.¹⁸ Such mathematical treatment allows one to obtain the interfacial shear stress σ and the complex shear modulus $G^*(= \sigma/\gamma)$ by solving the Stokes equations at low Reynolds numbers using the Boussinesq-Scriven model as the boundary condition at the interface. Our results are presented in the complex modulus notation with $G^* = G'(\omega) + iG''(\omega)$ where G' is the interfacial shear storage modulus and G'' is the interfacial shear loss modulus. These moduli are related to the real and imaginary parts of the complex interfacial viscosity by $G'(\omega) = \omega\eta_S''(\omega)$ and $G''(\omega) = \omega\eta_S'(\omega)$.

Brewster angle microscopy

The surface textures of the Langmuir films are visualized by Brewster angle microscopy (BAM). We use a MiniBAM (Nanofilm Technologie GmbH, Göttingen, Germany). The setup consists of a laser diode (30 mW and 660 nm), which produces a nearly linear polarized beam (p/s = 100/1), sent onto the aqueous phase with an angle $52 - 54^\circ$, ensuring Brewster's condition, i.e. no reflection for an ideally sharp interface.

The presence of an ultrathin film results in a small reflected intensity (typi-

cally, 10^{-6} times the incident beam intensity), but sufficient to detect the eventual presence of domains in the film, due to their different refractive indices. The images are recorded by using a CCD camera (60 Hz). In order to filter the residual scomponent background, a p-positioned analyzer is placed just before the CCD camera. The resolution of such an imaging system is below $20\mu\text{ m}$ and the field of view, which exhibits very low geometrical distortion, is $4.8 \times 6.4\text{ mm}^2$.

Results

Equilibrium compression isotherms

Fig. 1 shows the surface pressure isotherms ($\Pi - \Gamma$) measured for Langmuir films of PTBA ($M_n = 287\text{kDa}$; low polydispersity, PDI = 1.14) and PTBMA ($M_n = 211.5\text{kDa}$, PDI = 1.30; slightly polydisperse), spread onto an aqueous subphase at a temperature $T = 25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$.

As reported earlier by Maestro et al.,¹⁹ the isotherms corresponding to PTBA exhibit three regimes typical of an expanded polymer film in good solvent conditions:

- (1) A dilute regime, below the overlap concentration Γ^* . This concentration is quite low ($\Gamma^* \approx 0.2\text{mgm}^{-2}$), indicative of individual coils in an extended conformation. The film thickness was measured by ellipsometry and found close to the Kuhn length, $a = 0.45\text{ nm}$.¹⁹
- (2) A semidilute regime, in which the surface pressure scales as $\Pi \approx \Gamma^{3.8 \pm 0.2}$, corresponding to a Flory exponent $\nu = 0.70 \pm 0.05$, close to the good-solvent value in 2D ($\nu = 3/4$). This scaling behavior is compatible with the existence of a characteristic distance, decreasing with polymer concentration but independent of chain size, in agreement with de Gennes' picture of entangled chains in two dimensions. In this regime, the film thickness increases monotonously between $h \approx a$ and $h \approx 6$ to 7 nm .¹⁹
- (3) A concentrated regime occurring above Γ^{**} , in which the pressure and the film thickness are rather constant: $\Pi \approx 20\text{mN m}^{-1}$ and $h \approx 6 - 7\text{ nm}$.¹⁹

Similar isotherms were measured with the smaller M_n : they are shifted along the Γ axis, Γ^* and Γ^{**} being larger. The isotherms measured in this work are in full agreement with those reported in ref. 19.

Differently, PTBMA films exhibit a much sharper isotherm, which is characteristic of poor-solvent conditions. Indeed, due to its higher hydrophobicity, as compared to PTBA, the methacrylate homologue PTBMA is expected to collapse at the air/water interface: intra-chain interactions become favored over chain-water interactions, which are dominant in the case of PTBA. Consequently, PTBMA collapsed coils occupy less area than the swollen PTBA, yielding much lower adsorption pressures in the dilute regime (see Fig. 1). Then although PTBMA is more hydrophobic, it appears counterintuitively less surface active than PTBA. The PTBMA coils are observed to become into mutual contact at a higher concentration ($\Gamma^* \approx 0.4 - 0.5\text{mgm}^{-2}$) than PTBA.

Furthermore, in the semidilute regime, the pressure increases with a sharp slope $\Pi \approx \Gamma^{14.9 \pm 1.5}$, compatible with a Flory exponent corresponding to poor-solvent conditions, $\nu = 0.53 \pm 0.05$. Such condensed polymer films, made of collapsed chains, undergo a percolation-like transition to a solid-like state at $\Gamma \geq \Gamma^*$.^{20,21} Indeed, a sudden emergence of a finite surface pressure²² and elastic moduli occurs above the percolation threshold.^{21,23} At larger concentrations, above Γ^{**} , the surface pressure saturates: this is the "concentrated regime" (see Fig. 1).

Similar isotherms were measured with the smaller M_n : they are shifted along the Γ axis, Γ^* and Γ^{**} being larger as in the PTBA case.

Fig. 2a shows the effect of temperature (both polymers were studied in the range 16 – 40°C). PTBA shows a weak T -dependence, the isotherms slightly shifting towards lower densities with increasing temperature (Fig. 2a; left panel). In the studied temperature range, the Flory exponent remains essentially constant and equal to the good-solvent value (see inset in Fig. 2a; left panel). In contrast, PTBMA behaves differently. In this case, increasing temperature also causes the isotherms to shift towards lower densities, but the slope decreases significantly (Fig. 2a; middle panel). As the temperature increases between 16 and 40°C, the Flory exponent increases from poor- to good-solvent values (see inset in Fig. 2a; middle panel). This behavior suggests not only a thermal softening (decrease of the elastic modulus) but also a conformational change from the collapsed state at low T to a more extended conformation at high T . This effect is similar although less pronounced for PTBMA with a large M_n (Fig. 2a; right panel).

Fig. 2 b plots the values of the compression modulus, E_0 , calculated from the $\Pi - \Gamma$ isotherms (see eqn (1)) in Fig. 2a. As quoted, PTBA displays near-athermal behavior in the dilute and semidilute regime ($\Pi < 15 \text{mNm}^{-1}$). Values of the compression modulus are comparable to those found for similar acrylate¹⁹ and vinyl^{24–26} flexible polymers. In the concentrated regime ($\Pi > 15 \text{mNm}^{-1}$), some structural softening is detected at the highest temperatures as a decrease in the compression modulus at a given surface pressure. This softening is not due to a change in conformation (the exponent ν does not change) but likely to an increasing mobility, either of chain segments or of the chain as a whole. In contrast, for PTBMA, a significant structural softening is observed in all regimes upon increasing temperature as well as a conformation change (ν changes) (see Fig. 2b; right panel).

The compression modulus reaches a maximum at Γ^{**} : $E_0^{**} \approx 38 \text{mNm}^{-1}$ for PTBA, almost independent of the temperature. A higher value is found for PTBMA, at room temperature and below: $E_0^{**} \approx 45 \text{mNm}^{-1}$, as expected from its higher conformational persistence as compared to its flexible homologue PTBA. In this case, a significant drop of the compression modulus is observed at higher temperatures ($E_0^{**} = 28 \text{mNm}^{-1}$ at $T = 40^\circ\text{C}$), as expected from a softening transition occurring in this temperature range.

As shown with the PTBMA curves for the higher molecular weight, the effect of temperature is very similar whatever the M_n is, there are only shifts along the surface concentration axis as mentioned earlier for the surface pressure curves.

Oscillatory shear rheology

To get further insight into the mechanical dichotomy observed between PTBA and PTBMA films, we have studied their shear viscoelastic response in the concentrated regime, where differences in compressibility are observed to be larger. Fig. 3a shows the stress-strain plots ($\sigma - \gamma$), measured for PTBMA ($M_n = 211.5$ kDa) films at a constant surface concentration above Γ^{**} ($2.8 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \approx 2\Gamma^{**}$), corresponding to the concentrated regime. BAM images in Fig. 3b confirm that at this concentration, buckling or multilayered regions are absent (brighter bands parallel to the compression barriers in the case of buckling for instance). The shear response is significantly stronger even at very small deformations as compared to the response found for PTBA.¹⁹ In this case, a linear $\sigma - \gamma$ plot is only found at a small strain ($\gamma < 0.2\%$); above it, a plastic plateau emerges, the deformation increasing at a constant stress ($\sigma_Y \approx 0.3 \text{ mNm}^{-1}$). In the linear viscoelastic regime ($\gamma < 0.2\%$) the film behaves predominantly as a solid, with a very high shear modulus, $G' \approx 200 \text{ mNm}^{-1}$. In contrast, the loss modulus is comparatively smaller, $G'' \approx 70 \text{ mNm}^{-1}$, as expected for a solid. Note that this value corresponds to an enormous viscosity, $\eta_S \approx 100 \text{ g s}^{-1}$. The BAM image in Fig. 3b (left) confirms the solid-like character of the PTBMA. Holes appear spontaneously in the film resisting compression/ expansion. Formation and growth of holes has been previously reported in thin polymer films upon cooling, i.e. an annealing process.^{27,28} Here we report that an analogous process occurs due to polymer coils percolation upon compression in bad solvent conditions. Higher deformations ($\gamma > 0.2\%$) give rise to significant shear thinning with a progressive dominance of viscous flow over elasticity. At the intersection point ($G' \approx G'' \approx 20 \text{ mNm}^{-1}$, $\gamma \approx 2\%$), the system crossovers from a solid-like behavior to a viscoelastic regime dominated by viscous effects ($G'' > G'$). In contrast, holes are not formed in the fluid PTBA films at the same surface concentration as shown in Fig. 3b (right).

The films made with PTBMA of smaller molecular weights are less rigid, and concentrations well above Γ^{**} need to be used to retrieve a measurable shear modulus G' in the case of the smaller M_n (see Fig. 4). At these concentrations, the behaviors of G' and G'' versus strain are similar to those found for the larger molecular weight. Because we preferred to remain close to the semidilute limit (in order to avoid difficulties posed by buckling and multilayer formation) we decided to investigate further the shear properties of the films made with the largest M_n only.

In the case of PTBA, below a strain amplitude $\gamma = 10\%$, the shear response is too low to be measurable (see Fig. 4a) and, consequently, to ensure adequate accuracy we have worked with $\gamma = 20\%$. On the contrary, for PTBMA, adequate measurements in the linear regime can be performed at small strains (0.1% in this case).

In order to get further insight into the dynamic shear properties, we have measured the time-response in the linear regime. Fig. 5 shows the dependence of the viscoelastic parameters on the frequency of the applied deformation at

two different temperatures (16 and 40°C). For fluid PTBA films the shear storage modulus is very low ($G' \approx 0$, or below the lowest value experimentally resolvable). The loss modulus shows a significant increase with the deformation frequency, which is indicative of the existence of non-trivial relaxation dynamics. Independently of the temperature, the observed dependencies are close to power laws $G'' \approx \omega^{1.6 \pm 0.2}$ ($\omega > 1 \text{rads}^{-1}$ at 16°C). As expected, the viscosity decreases with temperature, thus smaller viscous losses are observed at higher temperature.

PTBMA exhibits comparatively different behaviors (see Fig. 5b). At low frequencies these solid-like polymer films exhibit a finite shear rigidity with $G' > G''$ (see also Fig. 3b). At low temperature (16°C), the elastic modulus is observed to increase weakly with frequency ($G' \approx \omega^{0.41 \pm 0.1}$) up to an angular frequency $ca. 20 \text{rads}^{-1}$, where a dynamic softening is observed: the yield strain is reached, leading to a decrease of the elasticity modulus. At high temperature (40°C) a much smaller (two orders of magnitude lower), constant, value of G' is observed at low frequencies. Similar yielding effects are observed at slower rates (ca. 0.2rads^{-1}), suggesting a higher mobility of the polymer chains. The loss modulus in Fig. 4b (right panel) also behaves differently to PTBA. A weak increase, $G'' \approx \omega^{0.39 \pm 0.1}$, is observed at low temperature (16°C). This rheological behavior resembles that of soft glassy materials.²⁹ As expected, a significant drop is observed in the viscosity coefficient upon increasing temperature, G'' taking values similar to those observed for PTBA. In this high temperature case (40°C), the G'' curve obtained for PTBMA films exhibits similar features than those found in the fluid PTBA films.

Thermal melting behavior

In order to confirm the presence of a possible melting transition with a rigid PTBMA, the temperature dependence of the shear viscoelasticity was measured at a constant frequency. In these experiments a concentrated film ($\sim 2\Gamma^{**}$) is prepared and left to equilibrate at room-temperature. Then, it is quenched by fast cooling into a low temperature state (5°C). After the film reaches thermal equilibrium, the viscoelastic parameters are measured during slow heating (temperature ramp of $+0.2^\circ\text{Cmin}^{-1}$). Data in Fig. 6 confirm the differences between the two polymers.

In the low-temperature quenched state (5°C), the shear modulus of PTBMA films takes a high value ($G' \approx 32 \text{mNm}^{-1}$), characteristic of a rigid solid. A counterintuitive small increase ($G' \approx 36 \text{mNm}^{-1}$) is observed in this case upon heating, indicative of the presence of a strong metastability probably induced by thermal quenching. Around 20°C a progressive decrease in the elastic modulus is detected up to 28 – 29°C, immediately followed by a sharp drop to a fluid-like value ($G' \approx 0$) at 32°C (see Fig. 6b). A similar behavior is observed for the viscosity coefficient, which remains essentially constant at low temperature (similarly to PTBA below 10°C, but with a viscosity about three orders of magnitude higher). Upon heating, the initial decrease in viscosity is not clearly

detected. Only at 28 – 29°C viscous premelting is clearly observed, which is immediately followed by a sharp drop of G'' at 32°C (see Fig. 6b). Remarkably, no reversibility was found: the solid state was not obtained back in cooling cycles performed with cooling rates similar to the above heating rates. Undercooling effects are therefore very strong in this system. Consequently, although the viscosity seems to drop for PTBMA nearly step-wise in a narrow temperature range, both, the lack of reversibility and the persistence of the high viscosity even when the elastic modulus is already decreasing, could be associated to a quasi-2D melting glass transition for PTBMA ($T_{\text{melt}} \approx 28 - 32^\circ\text{C}$) occurring at a temperature well below the bulk value ($T_g \approx 118^\circ\text{C}$).

Discussion

Similarly to bulk polymers,^{2,3} the macroscopic viscoelastic response of polymer films might be controlled by the intrinsic rigidity of the polymer backbone. We have studied the mechanical properties of Langmuir films made of two different polymers in which the presence of an additional methyl group enhances chain rigidity. While PTBA films are formed by flexible chains (good solvent conditions), PTBMA represents the case of almost collapsed coils (poor solvent conditions) (see Fig. 1). In compression, PTBA films show a near athermal behavior up to the concentrated regime but films made of PTBMA exhibit significant thermal softening (see Fig. 2). As concerns shear viscoelasticity, the differences in the thermal behavior are even more pronounced. While PTBA films in the concentrate regime ($\Gamma \approx 2\Gamma^{**}$) remain essentially fluid ($G' \leq 20\mu\text{ N m}^{-1}$) over the whole experimental temperature range (5 – 55°C), PTBMA films exhibit a fluid-solid transition characterized by a disappearance of the shear modulus.

For PTBA and PTBMA films at high temperature, the loss modulus follows nearly ω^2 -dependencies, indicating viscous shear thickening behavior. Conversely, the mechanical properties of the PTBMA films at low temperature exhibit weak frequency dependence ($G' \approx G'' \approx \omega^{0.4}$ at 16°C; see Fig. 4), in agreement with the theoretical expectation for a soft glassy material.²⁹ The soft glassy rheology (SGR) model proposed by Sollich et al.²⁹ predicts indeed that G' and G'' become independent of the frequency as T approaches T_g .

However, the thermal scenario presented in Fig. 6 does not resemble the typical bulk glass transition, for which the shear moduli increase considerably and more smoothly than shown in Fig. 6 as T_g is approached. Furthermore, G' and G'' are observed here to level off quickly beyond the transition temperature. Finally, the modulus is smaller than expected for usual glasses, typically above 1 GPa : if we estimate an equivalent bulk modulus dividing the surface modulus G' by the film thickness ($h \approx 10\text{ nm}$), we find a modulus of the order of 10 MPa only. Such a behavior has however been recently described by Sessoms et al.³⁰ in colloidal glasses, the colloids being soft polymer spheres. These authors suggest the presence of two transitions as the temperature is lowered, a first transition between a liquid state and a glassy state (at the colloidal scale)

and a second transition between a glassy state and a jammed state. While glass transition is due to the inhibited Brownian diffusion of polymer colloids past their neighbors due to the reduced available space, jamming occurs when the polymer colloids mutually contact forming a network. Hence, while temperature is the driving force responsible of the glass transition, the stress generated by polymer coil contacts leads to jamming.³⁰ In the PTBMA case, the polymer coils form isolated pancakes at the water surface in the dilute regime and come into contact at $\Gamma = I^*$. They therefore resemble closely the 3D system of soft spheres. On the basis of this analogy, data in Fig. 6 could be interpreted as follows: (1) at high temperature, G' and G'' are small as expected for a fluid layer; (2) upon cooling, both G' and G'' exhibit a sharp increase above a thermally driven glass transition, (3) upon further cooling, the polymer coils jam, and G' and G'' increase much more slowly due to friction between coils. The fact that G' and G'' increase much less than in the 3D soft sphere system may be due to an eventual thickening of the coils upon cooling, hence limiting frictional losses. Ellipsometry experiments are planned to clarify this point. However, within such a scenario, there should be some degree of reversibility, not observed here: the glassy state cannot be recovered upon cooling. Another possibility could be that despite the low value of G' , the glassy behaviour seen here at low temperatures is due to a collapsed conformation after solvent evaporation, with chain entanglements remaining frozen, leading to a solid-like film. Upon heating, the entanglements disappear and cannot reform (at least fully) upon subsequent cooling. In contrast, PTBA films remain fluid in the whole experimental temperature range due to the intrinsic flexibility of such a polymer, much larger than that of PTBMA.

Conclusions

In this work, we present the differences existing in the mechanical properties of Langmuir films made of PTBA and PTBMA as a consequence of its stronger intrinsic rigidity. Particularly interesting are the differences found in both acrylic polymer films as concerns their thermal behavior. While PTBA shows weak temperature dependencies upon compression or shear, the more rigid PTBMA exhibits significant thermal softening, which is accompanied by a conformational change from a collapsed state at low T to a more extended conformation at high T . A solidfluid transition is observed in PTBMA films upon heating, differently to PTBA which behaves as a fluid in the whole temperature range. At low temperature, the shear rheology of PTBMA films resembles that of soft glassy materials. Our results demonstrate the important role of backbone steric hindrances on the macroscopic mechanics in a reduced dimension.

By analogy with the behaviour of 3D dispersions of polymeric soft spheres, the observed transition could be a colloidal glass transition, followed by a jamming transition inhibiting a large viscosity increase. Another scenario could involve the disappearance of entanglements upon heating, which would account better for the lack of reversibility. In this case the glassy behaviour would be due to the

freezing of segmental motion as in pure 3D polymers. Further work is needed to clarify the mechanism of the transition.

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Fig. 1 Equilibrium surface pressure Π -surface concentration Γ isotherms at $T = 25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ of (\bullet) PTBA ($M_n = 287\text{kDa}$, $\text{PDI} = 1.14$) and (O) PTBMA ($M_n = 211.5\text{kDa}$, $\text{PDI} = 1.30$). Lines represent power-law fits to experimental data in the semidilute regime $\Pi \approx \Gamma^{2\nu/(2\nu-1)}$, providing values for the Flory exponent ν : PTBA, good solvent ($\nu \approx 0.7$); PTBMA, poor solvent ($\nu \approx 0.5$). Data from ref. 13. The arrows point the overlap concentration Γ^* at which polymer chains come into lateral contact, entering the semidilute regime, and Γ^{**} the concentration at which the chains become closely packed.

Fig. 2 Effect of temperature on (a) the equilibrium surface pressure Π surface concentration Γ isotherms and (b) the equilibrium compression modulus E_0 of polyacrylate Langmuir films. Comparison between PTBA of $M_n = 1.44\text{kDa}$ and $\text{PDI} = 1.13$ (\circ 16 and \ominus 40 $^\circ\text{C}$), PTBMA of $M_n = 1.45\text{kDa}$ and $\text{PDI} = 1.08$ (\square 16 and \blacksquare 40 $^\circ\text{C}$) and PTBMA of $M_n = 211.5\text{kDa}$ and $\text{PDI} = 1.30$ (\triangle 16 and \blacktriangle 40 $^\circ\text{C}$). Lines represent linear fits to experimental data in the semidilute regime, providing $\nu \approx 0.69$ for PTBA independently of the temperature (lines in Fig. 1(a) are almost parallel) and ν changing from 0.63 to 0.70 when increasing the temperature from 16 to 40 $^\circ\text{C}$ in the case of the lowest M_n PTBMA and from 0.54 to 0.56 in the case of the highest M_n PTBMA.

Fig. 3 (a) Evolution of the interfacial shear stress σ (\circ), interfacial storage G' (\square) and loss G'' (\circ) moduli as a function of the applied strain amplitude γ obtained at a constant frequency ($f = 0.1$ Hz) and temperature ($T = 25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$) for PTBMA of $M_n = 211.5\text{kDa}$ and $M_w/M_n = 1.30$ at a surface concentration in the concentrated regime where the largest differences in compression elasticity appear ($\Gamma = 2.8\text{mgm}^{-2}$). (b) BAM micrographs of both acrylic polymer films in the concentrated regime ($\Gamma = 2.8\text{mgm}^{-2}$). The presence of stable holes in the PTBMA film provides a first piece of evidence of the solid-like character of such a film as compared to PTBA.

Fig. 4 Evolution of the interfacial shear stress σ , interfacial storage G' (hollow symbols) and loss G'' (solid symbols) moduli as a function of the applied strain amplitude γ obtained at a constant frequency ($f = 0.1$ Hz) and temperature ($T = 25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$) for polyacrylate Langmuir films as a function of surface concentration. Comparison between (a) PTBA of $M_n = 1.44\text{kDa}$ and $M_w/M_n = 1.13$ at concentrations (O) 4.8 and (O) 9.7 mgm^{-2} and (b) PTBMA of $M_n = 1.45\text{kDa}$ and $M_w/M_n = 1.08$ at concentrations (Δ) 5.6 and (\square) 7.5 mgm^{-2} .

Fig. 5 Evolution of the interfacial storage G' (solid symbols) and loss G'' (hollow symbols) moduli as a function of the applied angular frequency ω at a constant strain amplitude γ for polyacrylate Langmuir films at two different temperatures, (a) $T = 16^\circ\text{C}$ and (b) $T = 40^\circ\text{C}$, at a surface concentration $\Gamma = 2.5\text{mgm}^{-2}$. Comparison between the values corresponding to (\square) PTBA of $M_n = 287\text{kDa}$ and PDI = 1.14, for which only the loss moduli can be measured and it appears to be almost independent of temperature and (O) PTBMA of $M_n = 211.5\text{kDa}$ and PDI = 1.30, for which both G' and G'' experience a sudden decrease when increasing the temperature.

Fig. 6 Temperature dependence of the (a) interfacial storage modulus G' and (b) interfacial loss modulus G'' of both polyacrylate Langmuir films ($\Gamma = 2.5\text{mgm}^{-2}$), obtained at a constant frequency ($f = 0.1$ Hz). Comparison between PTBA of $M_n = 287\text{kDa}$ and PDI = 1.14 (data have been obtained at $\gamma = 20\%$ in order to resolve such small G'' values) and PTBMA of $M_n = 211.5\text{kDa}$ and PDI = 1.30, for which a sharp decrease in both G' and G'' is measured (data have been obtained at $\gamma = 0.1\%$ in order to ensure a linear regime).